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SYSTEMATIZATION OF VARIETIES OF SEWING FITTINGS FOR PROTECTIVE CLOTHING OF AVIATION MILITARY PERSONNEL

***Abstract:** The aim of the work is to summarize information on the types of sewing fittings for protective clothing and equipment of military pilots. The article analyzes the range of modern sewing fittings and presents a list of the world's leading companies in their production. The most common types of fittings for protective clothing and equipment of military pilots have been identified and systematized. The materials used for its production are described. The design features of the types of sewing fittings are characterized, its functional capabilities are analyzed and the characteristic features are revealed. The results can be used in further design of protective clothing.*

Keywords: range of fittings, protective clothing, systematization, military aviation pilot

I. Introduction.

Modern military equipment includes a wide range of tools, which are functionally integrated into the systems of destruction, protection, energy supply, management and life support. The main task of material support of personnel is to meet their needs in uniforms, shoes, linen, bedding, equipment, special protective

clothing, personal protective equipment, depending on the tasks. One of the components of the pilot's protective equipment is sewing fittings for various purposes, the range of which is quite diverse. The expansion of the range of fittings for protective clothing and equipment is due to the emergence of innovative materials, modernization of manufacturing technologies taking modern requirements into account. Therefore, the structure of the range of sewing fittings requires careful study.

The analysis of sources revealed that the range of protective clothing for military pilots is quite diverse. It is known that in addition to uniforms, the military is provided with equipment, in the manufacture of which a significant component is the fittings. Insufficient level of study and partial coverage in some publications of information on the list and characteristics of sewing fittings confirms the relevance of the study and indicates the need for analysis of its varieties and their systematization on various grounds and creating an information base for further research.

II. Statement of the problem.

The scientific work [1] considers the use of plastic for the manufacture of fittings by the examples of materials for buttons and their quality characteristics. The authors note that the qualitative characteristics of the fittings determine its choice for light industry products of the selected purpose. Rational selection of plastic fittings is complicated by the lack of information on the required indicators and classification by composition and purpose. The authors of the article [2] analyzed the existing types of sewing fittings, provided their characteristics and methods of installation. In [3] the possibility of parametric modeling was investigated, which allows to develop fittings for clothes, shoes and accessories, in which electronic devices are integrated. The prospect of developing such products has been identified, which will attract the attention of technologists, engineers, fashion designers, designers and specialists from various industries. Innovative solutions and technologies in the manufacture of fittings, modern materials, equipment, including software allow you to expand the

range of these products, get a combination of different characteristics.

It was found that protective clothing of Ukrainian production for military aviation officers does not provide fully reliable protection against dangerous environmental factors, has design flaws and does not fully meet the specific level of requirements for it. Therefore, the systematization of varieties of modern fittings for protective equipment of the pilot on certain grounds is an important area of research and requires constant analysis.

It is known that fittings are auxiliary products for decorative design, fastening, locking, attaching, strengthening and ease of use of leathersgoods, textile haberdashery, garments and footwear [4]. The structure of the range includes zippers, fastex, frames, buckles, buttons, fasteners, blocks, eyelets, rivets, carbines, rings, textile fasteners, ribbons, cords and more.

A prerequisite for a rational and reasonable selection of materials and fittings is a careful study of the conditions of professional and qualification activities of the personnel [1]. Modern military pilot equipment includes protective clothing with a large number of structural elements, personal protective equipment, protective equipment, including a suspended parachute system and unloading system with bags for various types of equipment and purpose, which leads to the use of quality and reliable fittings to increase safety. To make protective clothing for military aircraft, the fittings must be durable, made of quality materials, as the pilot may be in a variety of climatic conditions while on duty, including high humidity, sudden changes in temperature, which can lead to equipment failures and be dangerous in emergency situations. Also, the fittings should provide convenience in the operation of garments, in particular reliable buttoning/unbuttoning, fastening, strengthening of individual areas [4], etc. It is used to transform protective clothing by fixing removable parts, changing their configuration and adjusting the parameters, which provides the ability to adjust the clothing to the morphological features of the military and increases the versatility of the product.

III. Results.

On the basis of the conducted researches the general systematization of kinds of fittings on the performed functions, material for manufacturing, a way of connection with the basic details of a product, a zone of placement is developed (fig. 1).

The most common materials for the manufacture of fittings for protective clothing are plastic, metal and its alloys, textiles, silicone, as well as a combination of these materials (e.g., galalite, acrylic, phenoplasts, aminoplasts, polystyrene, polyamides, polypropylene, polyethylene polyesters, etc.).

Modern plastic fittings, which account for the vast majority of them, are made on the basis of two components: acetal and nylon. Acetal is a thermostable plastic that gives the fittings high strength, rigidity, resistance to solvents. Nylon products are flexible, even under heavy loads, resistant to mechanical damage and low temperatures [5]. The disadvantage of nylon products is their significant loss of properties when interacting with water and in contact with solvents, in particular the reduction of resistance to loads and flexibility in environments with high humidity.

Metal fittings in most cases are made of aluminum, as it is one of the lightest metals and is durable. Such fittings are used in places with high loads.

An important indicator of the quality of modern fittings is the presence of IRR (Infra Red Reflective) processing (invisibility in the IR spectrum), which eliminates the reflection of products on night vision devices, which is especially important for military special equipment [6].

The world's leading companies for the manufacture of sewing fittings for various purposes for protective clothing are:

YKK (Japan) - a world leader in the production of fittings, in particular, zippers, fastex and textile fasteners;

– Due Emme (2M) (Italy) - a company dealing in the production of fittings from thermoplastic materials;

– Woojin plastic (Korea) - an advanced manufacturer specializing in military

fittings, including plastic fastex;

- Fidlock (Germany) - a company dealing in the manufacture of magnetic and mechanical fittings from plastic in combination with metal;
- Duraflex, ITW Nexus (USA) - companies focused on the manufacture of various types of fittings for military equipment, including fastex, buckles, etc;
- Giovanni Castiglioni (Italy) - a company dealing in the manufacture of fittings for clothing and haberdashery from plastic and metal [6, 7].

Figure 1 - General systematization of types of fittings for protective clothing for military aircraft pilots

There are also such companies as Dostband (Turkey), Coats (UK), which make contact-type fasteners for connecting products, securing components of protective equipment and fixing insignia. The leader is the company Velcro, which invented and patented textile fasteners. The leading domestic companies are Fibex (Ukraine) and ProCord (Ukraine), which produce various types of fittings and specialize in the production of textile tapes and cords, including paracord.

One of the most common types of fittings used in the design of protective

clothing is zipper. Its construction consists of two textile straps, which are attached to metal or plastic links, which are interconnected during the advancement of the lock [4]. Zippers are distinguished depending on the width of the links in the closed state and the type of lock (non-removable and detachable). By type of teeth, the zipper is divided into: tractor (cast), consisting of individual plastic teeth fixed on the tape; spiral (twisted) - made of synthetic fiber twisted into a spiral, which is sewn to the tape, or wound on it; metal with separate teeth; sealed, which includes tapes with waterproof impregnation and teeth, which in the fastened state are protected by a rubber profile (Fig. 2). By way of fastening: inseparable - with a limiter; detachable single-lock and double-lock - with a detachable limiter with a socket, movable and fixed pins; type "loop"; one-piece two-lock - O-shaped and X-shaped (Fig. 2). According to the shape of the manufactured products, there are zippers in a roll of free length and fixed [8,9]. There are also zippers by type of lock: auto-lock (symbol A/L), which contains a mechanism inside the slider and prevents the teeth from unbuckling at any position of the puller; pin-lock (symbol P/L) - a runner with stoppers (clamps) that block the teeth when the puller position is lowered; non-lock (symbol N/L) - without a locking mechanism.

Figure 2 - Graphic representation of the types of zippers: a - tractor; b - spiral; c - metal; d - detachable single-lock; e - detachable two-lock; f - detachable type "loop"; g - one-piece two-lock - O-shaped; h - one-piece two-lock - X-shaped

An integral element of various pilot equipment is the fastex type fastener, which connects the parts of the pilot's product and can withstand significant loads.

This is a pin-lock clasp consisting of two parts that are attached to the ends of textile tapes, straps, belts [9]. One part of the fastex fastener consists of a guide and side movable teeth for coupling, the other is a socket and contains grooves for fixing. Quick unfastening/fastening of the components of the fastener is done by clamping the side teeth or pressing a button. According to the method of fastening, fastex are distinguished with bilateral fixation, with fixation and adjustment, bilateral adjustment, quick installation (without sewing). By type they are distinguished to be rotary, with the button, three-point Y type, three-point with the lateral holder, five-point, with the central opening, with the magnetic lock (fig. 3).

Figure 3 - Graphic representation of varieties of fastex: a - bilateral fixation; b - with fixing and adjustment; c - bilateral regulation; d - quick installation; e - rotary; f - with a button; g - three-point Y type; h - three-point with a lateral holder; i - five-point; j - with central opening; k - with a magnetic lock

Frames and buckles are usually used in backpacks, bags, tactical systems and other components of military protective equipment. They are distinguished by size, materials, etc. It is known that the frame is an element for attaching a textile tape to the product [4]. The frame-regulator consists of a frame with membranes for fixing, dragging, adjusting the length and keeping the textile tape in a tight state. Buckles are

divided into two-slot, buckles-regulators are three-slot, buckles with a lock are two-slot and three-slot, with a bend (fig. 4).

Figure 4 - Graphic representation of the types of frames: a - metal; b - plastic; c - fast installation; d - triangular; e - for carabines; f - distributor; g - T-shaped adapter; h - adapter T of the form of fast installation; i - adapter for two belts crosswise and buckles; j - double slot; k - two-slot quick installation; l - three-slot regulator; m - three-slot regulator of fast installation; n - three-slot regulator with a bend; o - three-slot regulator with a bend of fast installation; p - the regulator three-slot with the lock; q - two-slot with a lock

According to the method of installation, there are conventional buckles and frames that require pre-installation in the absence of free ends of the tape; buckles and quick-mount frames (open) with an open loop, which can be installed directly into the finished product or used as a repair. Also, these types of fittings can be cast or with a movable crossbar.

The quick-release buckle is used in the shoulder systems of military backpacks. Its construction consists of three component plates, and the release process occurs by unfastening the plate, which provides for the fixing of the textile tape (Fig. 5) [10]. The buckle is equipped with a simple locking mechanism and opens under pressure, eliminating the possibility of accidental opening.

The fastening buckle is designed to connect bags of different purposes and special protective equipment, which provide slings for fastening (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 - Graphic image: a - quick release buckles; b - fastening buckles

The use of buttons and press fasteners is common for fastening clothes and fixing individual structural elements. Press fasteners are distinguished by the number of holes (with 2, 4 holes); by shape (round, oval), diameter, thickness, distance between holes, etc. Buttons with oval holes for textile tape are most often used for protective clothing of personnel, which provides ease of use and increased durability (Fig. 6).

Figure 6 - Graphic representation of the types of buttons: a - round with 2 holes; b - round with 4 holes; c - oval; d - round military

To limit the length of the components of the uniform use clamps that prevent the extension of cords, including elastic, from the drawstrings and allows you to fix them in the desired position. Clamps are distinguished by shape: round, round flat, column, oval; by the number of holes: with 1 hole, with 2 holes; by the method of fixation: sewn, with a hook, etc. (Fig. 7).

Figure 7 - Graphic representation of the types of clamps: a - round with the 1st hole; b - round flat; c - round sewn; d - column with the 1st hole; e - column with 1st hole and hook; f - column with the 1st hole sewn; g - a column with 2 holes; h - oval with 2 holes; i, j - oval with 2 holes sewn

Comfortable undergarment microclimate of protective clothing for personnel is achieved, among other things, by introducing into the design of sewing fittings, namely eyelets and machine eyelets (Fig. 8) [11]. They are designed to strengthen the edges of the holes in the products and prevent deformation during operation, for stretching and fixing cords, belts, etc. [4]. The machine eyelets has an additional part, a washer, which gives the joint more strength. The most common shape is round and oval eyelets (Fig. 8).

There are plastic, wooden and metal (galvanized steel, carbon steel, brass) eyelets and machine eyelets.

Figure 8 - Graphic representation of varieties: a - eyelet, b - round machine eyelet; c - oval machine eyelet; d - round ventilation insertion; e - rectangular ventilation insertion

Rivet is a metal clasp for one-piece connection of product parts, consisting of a hollow rivet pin and a head, which is a sleeve with a cover [4]. They are distinguished by the diameter of the head and the pin, the height of which depends on the thickness of the connected materials. It is used to strengthen the corners of pockets, textile tape in places of high load, etc. Among the varieties of rivets the most commonly used are one-sided, which consist of a pin with a flat base and a hat with a hemispherical base, and double-sided, with pins and hats with a hemispherical base (Fig. 9).

Figure 9 – Graphical image of a rivet: a – one-sided; b– two-sided

An important component of modern military pilot equipment is auxiliary accessories that ensure its functionality and ease of operation.

One of the types of auxiliary accessories is a puller - a suspension for the slider, which simplifies the grip of the slider to fasten / unfasten the zipper, especially

when using hand protection (Fig. 10). Pullers are made of textile tape, metal, plastic, silicone, band [9], etc.

To design, increase the strength and provide rigidity of the free ends of the band, selvage rand, belt, textile straps, a special clamp is used, which prevents them from falling out and deforming during operation [4]. Demountable clamps are most often used (Fig. 12).

Figure 10 – Varieties of pullers and clamps: a – puller made of textile strap; b – puller made of band; c- silicone puller; d–swing-up clamp; e – band clamp; f – textile strap clamp

During the performance of official duties, the pilot uses a large number of technical equipment and small fittings, so the equipment involves the use of carabiners and half-rings - spring-type locking mechanisms for connection and disconnection without damaging garments, for their secure fastening and, in the case of need, quick removal. Their varieties include a carabiner with a swivel, with a nut, a double carabiner of S type (Fig. 11).

Figure 11 - Graphic representation of the types of carbines: a - with a swivel; b - with a nut; c - S type

Among the types of auxiliary fittings used to secure the tubes of the hydrator, oxygen system and other equipment in the required position, a clip is well-known (Fig. 12). The quick-mount clip does not require fixing to the product with a threaded

connection, but is mounted on a sling. The system tube is fixed in a clamping connector, which is a rotary clip. A clip-tape for attaching bags for equipment is also well-known, made of thermoplastic material based on rubber, which has high strength, ductility, durability and does not deform during bending (Fig. 12). Half of the clip is equipped with holes for fixing the clip with screws or press fasteners and a hanging element.

The fittings also include a D-ring with a swivel mount, which allows to fix underbags and additional small equipment (Fig. 12).

Figure 12 - Graphic representation of the types of auxiliary fittings: a - quick-mount clip, b - D-ring quick-mount; in - a clip-tape

During designing of products use fittings both from plastic and metal, and from textiles to which belong tapes and cords, including elastic ones.

This type of fitting includes a textile clasp - a detachable product consisting of two pile tapes, one strip contains loops, the other - hooks that are connected by penetration of the coupling elements into each other. Among the indicators of the quality of the textile clasp, the shear and stratification efforts are important, the values of which should not be lower than the established norms [12]. The textile fasteners are distinguished by width, base density, load, fixation force, placement, type of hooks and loops, etc.

Among their varieties, a two-in-one clasp is known, consisting of a single ribbon with hooks and loops attached to it at the same time. It is used to adjust the length/width of the products, and the feature of this type of fastener is the location of the loops above the hooks, which does not cause discomfort in contact with the skin.

A modification of this type of fittings is also a fastener "on itself" for fastening products in a circle, consisting of one base with hooks placed on one side, and hinges

on the other.

There is also an elastic contact clasp, which consists of a loop part on an elastic base, is characterized by high elongation and provides a tight fit, adjustable with simultaneous fixation.

In the range there is also a mushroom-shaped textile clasp with a special design of hooks, which contributes to the highest bond strength, longitudinal and transverse displacement resistance.

Also use a "side by side" clasp with one base ribbon with hooks and loops on one side, which are located parallel to each other on different sides of the ribbon, which allows you to fasten it by folding it along (Fig. 13) [13].

Figure 13 - Graphic representation of the types of textile clasp: a - ordinary; b - mushroom-shaped; c - "on itself"; d - "two in one"; e - "side by side"

Textile straps are an integral part of rescue systems, tactical vests, equipment bags and other types of combat equipment. Its varieties differ in width from 5 to 75 mm, weight, surface density, type of weave and so on. Varieties of textile tape include sling, rep and kiper tape (Fig. 14). Kiper tape is a cotton ribbon with a diagonal or twill weave, which is made raw or smooth-dyed. Rep tail has a characteristic transverse hem on the weft and a sealed edge, made of polyester. Belt strap (sling) is a textile strap with high density, which has high wear resistance.

Figure 14 - Graphic representation of the types of textile tape: a - kiper; b - belt; c - rep

The elastic band is used to adapt the product to the morphological features of the personnel. It allows to adjust the width and volume of the components of the product, provides the necessary fit and varying degrees of fit of the product to the body in the necessary areas, which also prevents harmful substances from entering

the underwear space and reduces the negative impact of various environmental hazards. Elastic ribbons are distinguished by the method of weaving: fabric and knitted fabric. Woven elastic ribbon involves a complex interweaving of latex, cotton, viscose, which are intertwined with polyamide fibers. It also includes an auxiliary elastic band, which is made of high-density latex threads interwoven with polyester or polyamide thread. Auxiliary tape has a tight weave, which gives it high elasticity, wear resistance and increased strength. Knitted ribbon is made of cotton or linen threads, silk or artificial fibers, and elasticity is provided by latex threads. This tape is softer, malleable and elastic in contrast to woven, stiffer, resistant to abrasion and deformation. By type of design, the elastic band is divided into perforated, which has loops for buttons, and edging with a thinning along the center of the tape. Water, oil repellent and other impregnations are used to give the tapes different characteristics.

In addition to textile ribbons, cords are also used: round and flat, braided hollow and with a core, twisted, knitted and elastic. The elastic cord consists of a polyester braid and a core, which is a latex thread. Parachute systems and other equipment often use paracord, which is a cord made of nylon. Its distinctive feature is high wear resistance and strength due to the structure of the cord, filler and outer layer. The core of the paracord consists of several bundles depending on the required diameter of the cord and each of them contains even smaller bundles of twisted nylon threads [14].

Therefore, a reasonable choice of modern fittings for military pilot equipment should be given considerable attention, because it allows products to adapt to the morphological features of the military, provides quiet use, creates comfortable conditions for clothing space depending on climatic conditions, increases ergonomics. This is a promising area of designing high-quality military products with high reliability, ergonomics and more. The use of fittings also provides an opportunity to make changes in the design of the product by using the principles of transformation of individual items of clothing, which is an important area of design of multifunctional protective clothing.

IV. Conclusions

As a result of analytical research the types of sewing fittings for protective clothing and equipment of military pilots are analyzed, among which the most used are zippers, fastex, frames, buckles, buttons, press fasteners, blocks, eyelets, rivet, carabiners, rings, fasteners, braids, cords, etc. Their varieties are generalized and systematized according to various features, including purpose, material, area of placement, method of connection. The design and technological features of each type of fittings are characterized and revealed, namely zippers, fastex, frames, adjustable frames, rivets, buttons, carabiner, retainer, textile fastener, textile and elastic bands, etc. It is established that they all differ in shape, size, color, material, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Gavrilova, O.E., Nikitina, L.L. (2013), Influence of the quality of plastic accessories on the quality of light industry products [Vliyanie kachestva plastmassovoy furnitury na kachestvo izdeliy legkoy promyshlennosti], *Vestnik kazanskogo tekhnologicheskogo universiteta - Bulletin of Kazan technological university*, 2013, 22, pp. 164-166.
2. Rubanka, A.I., Tokar, H.M., Stelmakh, M.D., Horina, A.V., Ostapenko, N.V. (2018), Research of construction and technological solution of varieties of protective clothing for military aviation pilots [Doslidzhennia konstruktyvno-tekhnolohichnykh rishen riznovydiv zakhysnoho odiahu dlia pilotiv viiskovoi aviatsii], *Visnyk Khmelnytskoho natsionalnoho universytetu - Herald of Khmelnytskyi national university*, 2018, №1 (257), pp. 129-133.
3. Chumakova, S.V., Polischuk O.S. (2010). Inspection of sewing and shoe metal fittings, which are installed in light industry products by flaring and riveting [Ogljad shvejnoi ta vzuttevoi metalevoi furnituri, jaka vstanovljuet'sja u virobi legkoï promislovosti shljahom rozval'c'ovuvannja ta rozklepuvannja], *Visnyk Khmelnytskoho natsionalnoho universytetu - Herald of Khmelnytskyi national university*, 2010, 3, pp.104-110.

4. National standard of Ukraine, 1994. DSTU 3178-95 Accessories for haberdashery, textile haberdashery, garments and footwear. Terms and definitions. Kyiv: Derzhspozhyvstandart of Ukraine.
5. Plastykova furnitura z neilona ta atsetalu [Plastic fittings made of nylon and acetal], (2020), available at: <https://www.probag.com.ua/ru/tasmanian-tiger/35273-tasmanian-tiger-tac-modular-sw-pack-25-irr-stone-grey-olive.html> (accessed 28 December 2020).
6. Probag (2020), available at: <https://www.probag.com.ua/ru/tasmanian-tiger/35273-tasmanian-tiger-tac-modular-sw-pack-25-irr-stone-grey-olive.html> (accessed 28 December 2020).
7. YKK (2020), available at: https://www.ykkfastening.com/about_ykk/ (accessed 28 December 2020).
8. WoojinPlastic (2020), available at: http://www.woojinplastic.com/kr/product/list_product.php (accessed 28 December 2020).
9. National standard of Ukraine, 2018. DSTU EN 16732: 2018 (EN 16732:2015, IDT) Blinkers. Technical mind. Kyiv: Derzhspozhyvstandart of Ukraine.
10. Technical specifics, 2018. TC A01XJ.17223-062:2018 (01) Plastic accessories. Technical specifics of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine for items for speech security. Kyiv: Ministry of Defense of Ukraine.
11. Priazhka shvydkoho skydannia [Quick reset buckle], (2020), available at: <http://ronico.com.ua/pryazhka-bystrogo-sbrosa-2m-srs25-nato-green/> (accessed 28 December 2020).
12. Technical specifics, 2018. TC A01XJ.32412-093:2018 (01) Textile clasp. Technical specification of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine for items for material support. Kyiv: Ministry of Defense of Ukraine.
13. Kontaktna strichka [Contact tape], (2020), available at: <https://nylonfabric.ru/velcro> (accessed 28 December 2020).
14. Parakord ta yoho zastosuvannia [Paracord and its application], (2020), available at: https://tacticalstore.com.ua/articles/parakord_i_ego_primenenie (accessed 28 December 2020).